

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO TRANSFORMING THE CONTENT OF THE TUTORING MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The author argues that the tutoring model requires transformation in line with contemporary trends in education. The article presents conceptual approaches to transforming the content of the tutoring model, specifically focusing on technological and managerial aspects, which the author divides into two components: situational and procedural. The author examines the essence of each approach, their principles, as well as their focus on improving the tutoring model, enhancing its effectiveness, adaptability, and flexibility in a changing world.

Keywords: tutoring activity, tutoring process, technological approach, managerial approach, transformation, tutoring model.

The modern world is rapidly changing: digitization and technological advancements are defining significant shifts in people's lives through the lens of new intellectual and value-based opportunities. Consequently, changes are also occurring in education, which must respond to new conditions and challenges in societal development, reacting to new civilization challenges and societal realities, taking into account the trends and prospects of development both for individual states and the world as a whole. Prediction and determination of specific paths for implementing the tutoring model should be based on consideration of transformational processes inherent not only in modern education but also in civilization development itself. The tendency towards transformations in education is driven by a number of factors: reforms in education; the rapid development of information society; adaptation to the modern requirements for the formation of a personality capable of self-realization; raising educational standards; the relevance of acquiring competencies; rethinking the role of the teacher and the student.

The question of transformation in education is addressed in the works of O. Glushko and M. Tymenko, who conducted a terminological analysis of the concept of "transformation," which they interpret as a fundamental, structural, long-term, qualitative overhaul of the educational system with the introduction of innovations, containing components of reform and modernization. I. Tsupak and N. Pobirchenko consider transformations in education as a creative process of transferring essential features of innovative achievements of a certain educational profile to another educational profile with the aim of their unification.

In addressing the issue of transforming the content of the tutoring model, we consider it expedient to use a technological approach. As correctly pointed out by I. Dyckivska, "a significant feature of modern innovative processes in the field of education is their technologization - strict adherence to the content and sequence of stages in the implementation of innovations." The significance of the technological approach in transforming the content of the tutoring model lies in the fact that it

allows for: more accurately predicting the results of the tutoring process and managing it; analyzing and systematizing available practical experience and its use on a scientific basis; providing favourable conditions for the development of social-personal competencies of high school students; reducing the impact of adverse circumstances; optimally using available resources; selecting the most effective and developing new tutoring methods and models for solving pedagogical problems. Thus, the technological approach characterizes the direction towards improving tutoring activities, increasing its effectiveness, instrumentality, and intensity.

Considering the technological approach, tutoring activity can be viewed as an algorithmic process for solving specific tasks, consisting of the following stages: diagnosing the pedagogical situation, designing the outcome, and planning the tutor's activities; constructing and implementing the tutoring process; monitoring and adjusting the tutoring process; evaluating the obtained results and defining new tasks.

Scientific research on transforming the content of the tutoring model from the perspective of a technological approach manifests that the examined tutoring process is considered technological, which, thanks to a clearly defined sequence of steps aimed at achieving the planned goal, allows for achieving results with predefined quantitative and qualitative indicators and meets technological criteria. S. Vitvitska identified criteria for technological-ness, which, according to the researcher, include: conceptuality, viewed from the perspective of innovativeness, alternativeness, humanism, democratization, and modernity; systematicity; logicality of the process, consistency and interconnection of all its parts, expediency of individual elements, integrity; manageability (the ability to set goals, design the educational process, including the tutoring process, stage-by-stage diagnostics, variation of means and methods for the purpose of result correction); effectiveness (guaranteed achievement of the planned result); reproducibility; unity of content and procedural parts, their interdependence, complexity, adequacy to the

content of education and the contingent of educational subjects.

The concept of a technological approach in education is based on the concept of educational technology. According to UNESCO's definition: "Educational technology is a systematic method of creating, applying, and determining the entire process of teaching and knowledge acquisition, taking into account technical and human resources and their interactions, aimed at optimizing forms of education." N. Bilyk, S. Klepko, and P. Matviyenko consider that the main thing in educational technology is the "description of the design of the process of forming the student's personality, which guarantees pedagogical success," and the specificity of educational technology lies in the fact that it constructs and implements the educational process that must ensure the achievement of set goals. New methods emerge in response to challenges in society, as a result of scientific discoveries, or research. The process of developing tutoring methodological technology has gone through all stages of development: the emergence of a social need for individualization of education; fundamental research in psychology and pedagogy; development of new tutoring methods reflected in tutoring programs. Tutoring technology reflect the model of the tutoring process in a general secondary education institution as a component of the overall educational process, which also includes tutoring process management; it is local (in terms of application level) - implemented as a technology of individual parts of the educational process to solve specific didactic, educational, and developmental tasks. The advantages of tutoring technology lie in the fact that its structure can be independently developed according to the school's tasks or modernized, taking into account the specifics of tutoring activities.

Analysis of scientific literature has allowed us to identify the principles on which the implementation of tutoring technology is based: the principle of purposefulness, systematicity, subject-subject relations, humanization, innovativeness, integration, variability, creativity, forecasting, integrity of personality development, individualization, freedom of choice, cooperation, creativity, adaptability, and interactivity.

Tutoring technology is implemented directly in the interaction between the tutor and the student and is influenced by the personal and professional qualities of the educator, the level of their professional training, general culture, and mastery of tutoring technologies. Considering the humanistic essence of tutoring technology, orientation towards the integrity of the individual, integrability (psychological and pedagogical factors influencing the educational process), we can argue that the technological approach reflects the personal orientation of the tutoring process. In tutoring technology, this is always the choice of activity priorities, systems, and styles of interaction between the student and the tutor.

It is important for us that the technological approach involves the use of specialized technologies in tutoring, such as informational, health-preserving, creative development, communicative, competency development, reflection, empathy, and critical thinking,

which are relevant to our research. Constructing any pedagogical technology involves a certain algorithm, namely: development and justification of the technology; determination of the target purpose of the technology; creation of a tutoring activity program; integration of content, methods, types, and forms of implementing the tutoring process; determination of means of practical implementation of the technology in the tutoring process; conducting monitoring and assessment of students' competencies, their achievements, individual characteristics, and features.

The technological approach in transforming the content of the tutoring model is the basis for ensuring the technological level of designing the tutoring process, the high professionalism of tutor educators, their transition to research positions, the result of which can be the creation of qualitatively new products, namely new technologies.

The technological approach is closely linked with the managerial approach, consisting of procedural and situational approaches. The procedural approach is one of the modern effective management techniques and is used as a basis in international standards such as ISO series 21001:2018. The procedural approach involves systematic identification and management of processes and their interaction to achieve intended results in accordance with the goals and strategic plan of the educational organization. Characteristic features of the procedural approach include its orientation towards cross-functional processes and horizontal connections, as well as greater potential for improvement. Following the requirements of quality standards, we have identified that the application of a set of interdependent and interacting types of activities, their identification and management, constitutes a procedural approach.

In the context of the procedural approach, we interpret the management of the tutoring process as a series of interconnected actions (functions), each of which is a process in itself, defining the effectiveness of tutoring activities. The tutoring management process in schools includes functions of planning (deciding on the school's goals in implementing tutoring), organizing (creating a structure to achieve defined goals), motivating (creating conditions for educators' interest in tutoring work), controlling (ensuring goal achievement by setting standards, considering changes, comparing achievements with expected results), and regulating (eliminating deviations and deficiencies through appropriate measures), combined with communication and decision-making processes.

The implementation of the procedural approach in the context of tutoring involves defining the structure and sequence of tutoring processes in schools, with an emphasis on risk-based thinking aimed at leveraging opportunities and preventing undesirable outcomes. Risk-based thinking is particularly relevant today due to the uncertain situation we are in. Any such uncertainty can have positive or negative consequences, necessitating planning and implementation of actions to overcome risks and seize opportunities. The main advantage of risk thinking, according to A. Podustova, is the continuous improvement of tutoring management processes in schools through early identification of

"dangerous spots" in tutoring processes, which will ultimately increase the satisfaction of students and tutors with the results obtained.

According to the procedural approach, the desired result is achieved more effectively if all resources and types of activities are managed as processes, i.e., as a set of sequential actions. In this case, quality issues of the tutoring process should be embedded in each process. This approach allows us to identify priority directions for the development of the tutoring model, predict the results of tutoring activities, assess opportunities for improvement, and more effectively utilize resources and reduce costs for tutoring activities.

The situational approach logically extends the procedural approach, as it also relates to management theory and represents a certain way of thinking that considers specific situations. This approach involves identifying factors that have created a particular situation and are most influential, determining the strengths and weaknesses, limitations, and consequences of the situation, and selecting specific approaches and methods to address the problem for that specific situation. L. Chorna and S. Kudlaienko emphasize that the situational or case approach to management is more of a way of thinking than a set of specific actions.

Today, principals of secondary education institutions engage in managerial activities by addressing a range of daily situations of various kinds and plans. This requires them to change the management system in a short period with a view to achieving long-term results effectively, using both traditional and innovative approaches, the ability to comprehensively address issues, analytical thinking, and changes in ways of interacting with people (educators, students, parents, government representatives, community, local government leadership) according to the "needs of the day," and more.

Using the situational approach to transform the content of the tutoring model facilitates more effective goal achievement in changing conditions and with numerous and complex tasks, as it can align parts of the whole, combining them. Based on the situational approach, it becomes possible to consider a maximum number of factors from the internal and external environment, with the school administration focusing on utilizing opportunities for the direct application of science to specific situations and conditions. The situational approach involves making decisions as potential problems are identified, not according to established plans. This approach requires a significant level of decentralization in the management of secondary education institutions, thus providing the necessary adaptability and flexibility of the organizational structure and a rapid response to constantly changing conditions.

According to the definition by T. Rohova, the methodology of the situational approach involves a four-step process:

1. School leaders and teachers should be familiar with management methods and tools.

2. School leaders should be able to anticipate potential consequences, both positive and negative, of applying any methodology or concept.

3. School leaders should be able to interpret the situation correctly.

4. School leaders should be able to relate specific methods and tools that would have the least negative effect and the fewest drawbacks to specific situations.

We also agree with the researcher that the situational approach can be considered one that excludes the formal aspect in managing the educational process, particularly tutoring, and focuses on the individuality of the teacher and student.

The situational approach determines the management of processes in secondary schools based on the following basic principles: flexibility; openness; feedback; variability; reflexivity. The situational approach involves not only identifying the factors that led to the situation but also establishing their priority, strength of influence, investigating potential consequences and threats. Accordingly, the selection of specific decisions regarding the situation that has arisen is important in the situational approach (based on the analysis conducted).

The situational approach is capable of ensuring high adaptability of the educational institution to external changes since it contributes to balancing the system, bringing individual parts into alignment with the whole, and combining them. The cornerstone of the situational approach in transforming the content of the tutoring model is a set of changing circumstances occurring within and outside the school system that influence it over a specific period of time. We agree with the opinion of O. Polyak, who argues that the situational approach enables decision-making based on analysis and understanding of the situation, its dynamics, rather than relying on the traditional "trial and error" principle. The ability to conduct preliminary analysis of the situation and anticipate its expected changes makes the situational approach much more effective and helps avoid significant resource and time losses.

Therefore, in our opinion, the application of technological and managerial (situational and procedural) approaches to transforming the content of the tutoring model will contribute to defining the main tasks and directions of activity of the general secondary education institution within the implementation of the tutoring process.

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